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EFFECT OF COMPUTER APPRECIATION ON READING COMPREHENSION OF STUDENTS WITH LOW VISION USING NON-VISUAL DESKTOP ACCESS IN UNIVERSITY OF JOS

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Abstract: *This study investigated the effect of computer appreciation on the reading comprehension of students with low vision through the use of Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) at the University of Jos. Three objectives, three research questions, and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A single-subject experimental research design was adopted. The target population comprised 17 first-year students with visual impairment in the Department of Special Education and Rehabilitation Sciences, University of Jos. The sample consisted of five 100-level students with low vision and adventitious visual impairment, aged between 18 and 25 years. Simple percentages were used to answer the first and second research questions, while mean scores (\bar{x}) were used to address the third and fourth research questions. The hypotheses were tested using the *t*-test at 0.05 level of significance, with data coded and analyzed using SPSS version 23. The findings revealed that exposure to computer appreciation enhances the reading comprehension and knowledge acquisition of students with low vision. Based on these findings, the study recommended that government agencies should support higher institutions by providing computers to improve students' information and communication technology (ICT) skills. In addition, special educators of learners with visual impairment should advocate for the use of Non-Visual Desktop Access, as it is a free, user-friendly, and easily installable assistive software for students with low vision.*

Keywords: Computer Appreciation, Reading comprehension, Low vision, Non-visual desktop access, Jos

Introduction

Reading is a complex cognitive process that involves decoding written symbols in order to construct meaning, commonly referred to as reading comprehension. It entails the recognition of printed or written words and the understanding of their meanings, as well as the systematic study of written texts and documents. Reading may also be described as a linguistic skill grounded in auditory knowledge of language, where “auditory” implies familiarity with the sounds and spoken forms of words. As a fundamental means of language acquisition and communication, reading enables the sharing of information and ideas. It represents a dynamic interaction between the reader and the text, influenced by the reader’s prior knowledge, experiences, attitudes, and linguistic background within specific cultural and social contexts (UNESCO, 2015).

Visual impairment refers to any degree of damage to an individual’s visual functioning that interferes with daily living and learning. Learners with visual impairment may experience a range of visual conditions, including loss of central vision or peripheral vision. From a medical perspective, visual impairment encompasses any form of vision loss that may result in partial sight or complete absence of sight, including total blindness or legal blindness (Soduin, 2016). Vision, as it relates to eyesight, involves the brain’s interpretation of visual information received from the eyes. When this process is disrupted due to injury, disease, or congenital factors, visual impairment occurs, similar to impairments affecting other parts of the human body.

Visual impairment occurs in various forms and is broadly classified according to the time of onset into two major categories: congenital and adventitious. Congenital visual impairment is present at conception or birth and may result from hereditary or other prenatal factors. In contrast, adventitious visual impairment develops after birth and is often described as acquired or developmental vision loss. Individuals with visual impairment differ considerably, as the age of onset significantly influences the type of rehabilitation and educational support required. Visual impairment may also be classified based on severity into mild, moderate, and severe categories (WHO, 2021). While some individuals are completely blind and have no light perception, others retain partial vision, such as the ability to perceive light and darkness or limited visual details. Broadly, visual impairment can be categorized into total blindness and low vision.

Khurana (2012) described individuals with adventitious low vision as those who were previously sighted but later experienced partial loss of vision, resulting in educational and rehabilitative needs that differ from those of individuals with congenital low vision. Learners with adventitious low vision often require less time to acquire reading and comprehension skills due to prior visual experience, brain development, and exposure to print. In contrast, learners with congenital visual impairment typically experience greater difficulty in understanding visually related concepts because they lack early visual experiences.

Many learners with visual impairment traditionally rely on Braille for reading and writing, as well as voice-based communication and typewriting. Although Braille is an effective literacy medium, it can be challenging to master and requires considerable time and practice to develop tactile word recognition skills. Advances in technology have, however, created opportunities for individuals with visual impairment to learn more efficiently through the use of computer-based assistive technologies, such as screen reader applications, enabling them to access information in ways similar to their sighted peers. To effectively utilize such applications, learners with visual impairment must acquire basic computer literacy skills through computer appreciation programmes. Computer applications are software programs developed to assist users in performing specific tasks efficiently (Adeeko, 2012).

Screen readers represent a key category of computer applications that support learners with visual impairment. However, their effective use depends largely on the user's level of computer literacy, which can be developed through computer appreciation. Computer appreciation involves familiarizing users with basic computer operations and applications that support everyday tasks such as word processing, data computation, communication through emails, entertainment, and multimedia use.

Screen readers are assistive technology applications that use synthetic speech output to read aloud text and Braille content displayed on computer and mobile device screens, making digital information accessible to both sighted individuals and persons with visual impairment. One of the most efficient and widely used modern screen readers for learners with visual impairment particularly those with low vision is the Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) application. NVDA is a free and open-source screen reader developed by Michael Curran and James Teh, two partially sighted computer programmers from Australia. The application was designed to enhance digital accessibility and improve the quality of life of persons with blindness and low vision worldwide (NVDA, 2014). Despite its availability, students with visual impairment at the University of Jos largely depend on Braille machines and other commercial screen readers, many of which are costly and beyond the financial reach of most students. As a result, students with low vision often experience difficulties in reading and comprehending Braille texts. This study therefore seeks to address challenges associated with reading comprehension by utilizing Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) to meet the specific learning needs of students with low vision through improved computer literacy skills.

Statement of the Problem

Learners with visual impairment at the University of Jos are significantly affected by their visual condition, which negatively impacts their reading comprehension and overall academic performance. Reading is a demanding task even for sighted learners; consequently, it poses greater challenges for learners with visual impairment. Difficulties in visual perception limit their ability to read efficiently, thereby affecting comprehension and academic achievement.

Observations indicate that Braille is the primary medium of reading for students with visual impairment in the university. However, Braille reading has been reported to be considerably slower than print reading. In comparing Braille and print reading, Abang (2005) noted that Braille reading is not only slower but also more demanding, frustrating, and monotonous. Given that reading speed is closely related to comprehension, slower reading rates may further hinder effective comprehension among learners with low vision. Consequently, reliance on Braille alone may reduce reading efficiency and academic productivity. The physical and cognitive demands associated with Braille reading can also lead to fatigue, making the learning process cumbersome and discouraging for students. These challenges underscore the need for an alternative, computer-based reading system that can support efficient access to learning materials.

Ahmed (2016) emphasized that computers have become indispensable tools that have transformed modern life, with applications across schools, homes, offices, hospitals, and correctional institutions. In contemporary society, basic computer literacy is essential for effective participation in education and daily activities, including for persons with visual impairment. In the educational context, information and communication technologies (ICTs), such as screen reader applications like NVDA, have significantly improved access to teaching, learning, and research resources. Teaching reading to learners with visual impairment remains a complex task due to individual differences among learners, which teachers must consider during instructional planning and delivery. Moreover, even when assistive technologies such as NVDA are available, their effectiveness is limited if learners lack the

necessary computer literacy skills to operate them. Since screen readers are computer-based applications, users must possess foundational computer appreciation skills to utilize them effectively. The present study therefore seeks to provide computer appreciation training to enable students with low vision at the University of Jos to competently operate computers and effectively utilize the Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) application for improved reading comprehension.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to examine the effect of computer appreciation on the reading comprehension of students with low vision through the use of Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) at the University of Jos.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the performance level of students with low vision in a reading comprehension cloze test;
2. assess the reading comprehension performance of students with low vision prior to the intervention; and
3. examine the reading comprehension performance of students with low vision after the intervention.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students with low vision in the reading comprehension cloze test?
2. What are the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students with low vision in the reading comprehension passage exercise?
3. What are the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students with low vision in the computer appreciation competency test?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students with low vision in the reading comprehension cloze test between the pre-test and post-test.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students with low vision in the computer appreciation competency test between the pre-test and post-test.
3. There is no significant mean difference in the computer competency test between the pretest and post-test mean scores of the students with low vision.

Methodology

Research Design

A single-subject experimental research design was adopted for this study. This design is particularly appropriate for determining the effectiveness of instructional materials, interventions, or strategies when working with an individual or a small group of participants whose outcomes are to be closely documented. Single-subject research focuses on establishing the effects of an intervention on individual participants and relies on control procedures rather than the use of a separate control group. As noted by Orme and Cox (2001), participants in single-subject research serve as both the control and the experimental group.

Population of the Study

The target population for this study comprised 17 first-year students with visual impairment in the Department of Special Education and Rehabilitation Sciences at the University of Jos.

Sample Size and Characteristics

The study sample consisted of five 100-level students with low vision, including three males and two females with adventitious visual impairment, aged between 18 and 25 years.

Sampling Technique

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants for the study. According to Awotunde, Ugodulunwa, and Ozoji (2002), purposive sampling is a judgmental sampling method in which the researcher deliberately selects participants considered to be representative of the population relevant to the research problem. In this study, the focus was on students with low vision, making purposive sampling appropriate.

Instrumentation

Two instruments were used for data collection: the Computer Application Competence Test (CACT) and the Reading Comprehension Competence Test (RCCT). Both instruments were administered at the pre-test and post-intervention stages of the study. The CACT consisted of 15 items designed by the researcher to assess basic computer knowledge and application skills among students with visual impairment. Similarly, the RCCT comprised 15 items developed from reading comprehension passages commonly taught at the senior secondary school level in Nigeria, and the questions were structured in line with established evaluation guidelines.

Statistical Analysis

For data analysis, simple percentages were used to answer the first and second research questions, while mean scores (\bar{x}) were used to address the third and fourth research questions. The null hypotheses were tested using the t-test at the 0.05 level of significance. All data were coded and analysed using the SPSS version 23.

Results

Research Question One:

What is the pretest post-test mean score in Reading Comprehension Cloze test if students with Low Vision?

Table 1: Pretest Post-test Result in Reading Comprehension Cloze test

S/N	Students	Pretest			Posttest			Difference	
		NO.	%	\bar{X}	NO.	%	\bar{X}	NO.	%
1	A	15	30	33.2	32	64	69.6	17	34
2	B	17	34		30	60		13	16
3	C	13	26		33	66		20	40
4	D	18	36		40	80		22	44
5	E	20	40		38	78		18	36

Table 1 presents the pre-test and post-test performance of students with low vision in the reading comprehension cloze test. The results indicate that Student A obtained a score of 15 (30%) in the pre-test and 32 (64%) in the post-test, reflecting an improvement of 34 percentage points following the intervention. Student B scored 17 (34%) in the pre-test and 30 (60%) in the post-test, showing a 26 percentage-point improvement after treatment. Student C recorded a pre-test score of 13 (26%) and a post-test score of 33 (66%), representing a 40 percentage-point increase in performance.

Furthermore, Student D achieved a pre-test score of 18 (36%) and a post-test score of 40 (80%), indicating a 44 percentage-point improvement. Student E recorded a pre-test score of 20 (40%) and a post-test score of 38 (78%), reflecting a 38 percentage-point increase. Overall, the lowest pre-test score was 13 (26%), while the highest pre-test score was 20 (40%). In contrast, post-test scores ranged from a minimum of 32 (64%) to a maximum of 40 (80%). The mean pre-test score was 33.2, whereas the mean post-test score increased substantially to 69.6, indicating marked improvement in reading comprehension performance following the intervention.

Research Question Two:

What is the pretest Post-test mean score in the Reading Comprehension passage exercise?

Table 2: Pretest Post-Test Mean Score in Reading Comprehension Passage Exercise

S/N	Students	Pretest			Posttest			Difference	
		NO.	%	\bar{X}	NO.	%	\bar{X}	NO.	%
1	A	3	30	33.2	5	50	69.6	3	30
2	B	2	20		6	60		4	40
3	C	2	20		6	60		4	40
4	D	4	40		7	70		3	30
5	E	3	30		5	50		2	20

Table 2 presents the pre-test and post-test performance of students with low vision in the reading comprehension passage exercise. The results indicate that Student A obtained a pre-test mean score of 3 (30%) and a post-test mean score of 5 (50%), representing a 20 percentage-point

improvement following the intervention. Student B recorded a pre-test mean score of 2 (20%) and a post-test mean score of 6 (60%), showing a 40 percentage-point improvement after treatment.

Similarly, Student C scored 2 (20%) in the pre-test and improved to 6 (60%) in the post-test, reflecting a 40 percentage-point increase in performance. Student D achieved a pre-test score of 4 (40%) and a post-test score of 7 (70%), which was the highest post-test score recorded, indicating a 30 percentage-point improvement. Student E obtained a pre-test score of 3 (30%) and a post-test score of 5 (50%), resulting in a 20 percentage-point improvement.

Overall, the lowest pre-test score was 2 (20%), while the highest pre-test score was 4 (40%). In contrast, post-test scores ranged from a minimum of 5 (50%) to a maximum of 7 (70%). The mean pre-test score was 28, whereas the mean post-test score increased to 58, demonstrating a substantial improvement in reading comprehension performance following the intervention.

Research Question Three:

What is the pretest post-test Mean Score in Computer Appreciation Competency Test of Students with Low Vision?

Table 3: Pretest Mean Score in Computer Appreciation Competency Test

S/N	Students	Pretest			Posttest			Difference	
		NO.	%	\bar{X}	NO.	%	\bar{X}	NO.	%
1	A	4	40	140	9	90	70	5	50
2	B	3	30		8	80		5	50
3	C	3	20		7	70		4	40
4	D	2	30		6	60		4	40
5	E	2	20		5	50		3	30

Table 3 presents the pre-test and post-test mean performance of students with low vision in the computer appreciation competency test. The results show that Student A recorded a pre-test mean score of 4 (40%) and a post-test mean score of 9 (90%), indicating an improvement of 50 percentage points following the intervention. Student B obtained a pre-test mean score of 3 (30%) and improved to 8 (80%) in the post-test, reflecting a 50 percentage-point increase in performance.

Similarly, Student C scored 3 (30%) in the pre-test and 7 (70%) in the post-test, representing a 40 percentage-point improvement. Student D recorded a pre-test mean score of 2 (20%) and a post-test mean score of 6 (60%), indicating a 40 percentage-point improvement. Student E achieved a pre-test score of 2 (20%) and a post-test score of 5 (50%), reflecting a 30 percentage-point improvement.

Overall, the lowest pre-test score was 2 (20%), while the highest pre-test score was 4 (40%). In contrast, post-test scores ranged from a minimum of 5 (50%) to a maximum of 9 (90%). The mean pre-test score was 28, whereas the mean post-test score increased substantially to 70, demonstrating marked improvement in computer appreciation competency following the intervention.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant mean difference in the reading comprehension cloze test performance between the pretest and posttest scores of the students with low vision.

Table 4: Pretest and posttest scores on reading comprehension cloze test performance students with low vision

S/N	Groups	\bar{x}	SD	df	Level of Sig.	t-cal	P-value
1	Pretest	33.2%	5.40	4	0.05	13.75	0.000
2	Posttest	69.6%	8.87				

Table 4 presents a comparison of the pre-test and post-test mean scores for the reading comprehension cloze test performance of students with low vision. The pre-test mean score was 33.2 with a standard deviation of 5.40, while the post-test mean score increased to 96.6 with a standard deviation of 8.87. The calculated t-value was 13.73, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This result confirms that the intervention led to a significant improvement in the reading comprehension cloze test performance of students with low vision.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant mean difference in the reading comprehension passage exercise performance between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the students with low vision.

Table 5: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores on Reading Comprehension Passage Exercise Performance of Students with Low Vision

S/N	Groups	\bar{x}	SD	df	Level of Sig.	t-cal	P-value
1	Pretest	28.0%	8.00	4	0.05	7.48	0.002
2	Posttest	58.0%	8.36				

Table 5 shows the comparison between the pretest and posttest mean scores of students with low vision. Before intervention, the pretest mean score was 28.0 with standard deviation of 8.00. After intervention, the posttest mean score was 58.0 with standard deviation of 8.36. The t-calculated was 7.48 and the P-value was 0.002. This shows a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the students. Since the P-value was less than the 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This connotes a significant mean difference in reading comprehension passage exercise performance between the pretest and posttest scores of the students with low vision.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant mean difference in the computer appreciation competency test between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the students with low vision.

Table 6: Pretest and Posttest mean scores on computer appreciation competency of students with low vision

S/N	Groups	\bar{x}	SD	df	Level of Sig.	t-cal	P-value
1	Pretest	28.0%	8.36	4	0.05	7.48	0.002
2	Posttest	70.0%	15.81				

Table 5 presents a comparison of the pre-test and post-test mean scores for the computer appreciation competency test performance of students with low vision. The pre-test mean score was 28.0 with a standard deviation of 5.40, while the post-test mean score increased to 70.0 with a standard deviation of 15.81. The calculated t-value was 7.48, with a p-value of 0.002, indicating a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This result demonstrates that the intervention significantly improved the computer appreciation competency of students with low vision.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that students with low vision performed poorly in the reading comprehension cloze test at the pre-test stage. Pre-test scores ranged from a minimum of 13 (26%) to a maximum of 20 (40%), indicating low baseline reading comprehension ability among the participants. However, following the intervention, there was a marked improvement in performance, with post-test scores ranging from 30 (60%) to 40 (80%). The mean score after the intervention increased to 69.6%, demonstrating the effectiveness of computer appreciation using Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) in enhancing reading comprehension among students with low vision. These findings are consistent with those of Kartikasari and Lestiono (2017), who reported that students with visual impairment encounter significant challenges in learning English, particularly in reading, and therefore require additional instructional support and conducive learning environments to improve their language skills. This suggests that learners with low vision benefit substantially from targeted instructional interventions and assistive technologies.

Similarly, the results of the reading comprehension passage exercise showed that students' performance was low at the pre-test stage, with two students scoring as low as 2 (20%) and the highest pre-test score being 4 (40%). After the intervention, students demonstrated notable improvement, as post-test scores ranged from 5 (50%) to 7 (70%). The mean score increased from 28% at the pre-test to 58% at the post-test, further confirming the positive impact of the intervention. This finding aligns with Ghafri (2015), who observed that students with visual impairment tend to read more slowly than their sighted peers because they process text at the letter level rather than as complete words, resulting in frequent pauses during reading. The improvement recorded in this study suggests that the use of assistive technology such as NVDA can mitigate these challenges by enhancing access to textual information and supporting comprehension.

Furthermore, the study revealed that students with low vision exhibited low performance in the computer appreciation competency test at the pre-test stage, with scores ranging from 2 (20%) to 4

(40%). However, following the intervention, their performance improved considerably, with post-test scores ranging from 5 (50%) to 9 (90%). The mean score increased from 28% before the intervention to 70% after the intervention, indicating a substantial gain in computer literacy skills. This finding supports the view of Ahmad (2016), who emphasized that computers have become indispensable tools in modern society, used across educational, professional, and social settings. Consequently, it is imperative that students with low vision acquire computer literacy skills, particularly in the use of screen reader applications such as NVDA, to enhance academic performance and independence.

The hypothesis testing results further confirmed the effectiveness of the intervention. For the first hypothesis, the pre-test mean score was 28.0, while the post-test mean score increased to 58.0, with a standard deviation of 8.36. The calculated t-value of 7.48 and a p-value of 0.002 indicated a statistically significant difference in reading comprehension cloze test performance between the pre-test and post-test. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

Similarly, the second hypothesis showed a pre-test mean score of 28.0 and a post-test mean score of 58.0, with a standard deviation of 8.36. The t-calculated value of 7.48 and p-value of 0.002 revealed a significant difference in students' performance in the reading comprehension passage exercise between the pre-test and post-test. Accordingly, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Finally, the third hypothesis revealed that the pre-test mean score in the computer appreciation competency test was 28.0%, while the post-test mean score increased to 70.0%, with a standard deviation of 8.36 and a p-value of 0.002. This result indicates a significant difference in computer appreciation competency between the pre-test and post-test. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that computer appreciation using NVDA significantly improved both computer literacy and reading comprehension among students with low vision.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that students with low vision must actively engage in reading to enhance their knowledge and academic skills. Reading is a fundamental component of most educational activities and is essential for accessing information. The study highlights the importance of integrating Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) applications to support reading by allowing students to listen to text and comprehend it in a manner similar to sighted individuals. Effective use of such applications, however, requires the acquisition of basic computer skills, underscoring the need for computer literacy training among students with low vision.

Recommendations

In light of the study findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Students with visual impairment whose family and friends are financially capable should consider providing them with computers, particularly desktop computers, to support reading comprehension and learning.
2. Students with visual impairment should actively acquire computer knowledge and skills, as they possess the intellectual capacity to learn and can benefit from technology-based instruction.
3. Educational institutions should provide laptops or desktop computers in resource rooms to support students with visual impairment who cannot afford their own devices.

4. Government agencies should support higher institutions of learning by providing computers and assistive technology to enhance students' knowledge and skills in information and communication technology (ICT).
5. Special educators should advocate for the use of Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA) applications, as they are free, easy to install, and highly effective in supporting students with low vision.
6. Parents of children with visual impairment, especially those in higher education, should ensure access to computers to facilitate academic performance and independent learning.

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